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Zone-Selective Plant Protection based on AI Pest Early Detection

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Summary

Vine *downy mildew* and *Apple scab* are endemic diseases that cause severe losses when not detected and treated at an early stage. On the other hand, reducing the use of pesticides in fruit production is a major global societal challenge and is in line with the European *Green Deal* and EU Directive 2009/128/EC, demanding integrated pest management as well as with 2016/2031/EC, which requires that a proportionate and effective response to plant health threats is established through a combination of technological, ecological and institutional management.

Thus, on the quest for more targeted treatments, the EU Horizon 2020 OPTIMA research project (<http://optima-h2020.eu/>) addresses this problem through a.) an image analysis based pest *Early Detection System* (EDS) b.) post processing in a custom *Decision Support System* (DSS), as well as c.) downloading of generated application maps to cloud connected spraying equipment for precise application in desired application zones.

Although, knowing that the majority of treatments against *Vine downy mildew* and *Apple scab* are of preventive and not of curative nature, selecting these frequent pests allowed the OPTIMA partners to prove that the underlying technologies and algorithms are able to support “Zone-Selective Plant Protection based on AI Pest Early Detection”.

Key words: Integrated pest management, IPM, *downy mildew*, *Apple scab*, artificial intelligence, AI, edge computing, variable rate application, OPTIMA.

Introduction

According to the *World Health Organization* (WHO), low fruit and vegetable intake causes approximately 1.7 million deaths per year (WHO, 2019). At the same time, studies predict serious fruit shortages up to 2050, with the world population reaching 9 billion (Grethe *et al.* 2011), while pests and diseases are responsible for 25 % to 40 % yield loss before harvest globally (FAO, 2020). At the same time the *European Food Safety Authority* (EFSA) announced that more than 45 % of food products contain pesticide residues (EFSA, 2021). Thus, reducing the use of pesticides in fruit production is a major global societal challenge and it is in line with European Directive 2009/128/EC, demanding *integrated pest management* (IPM) as well as with 2016/2031/EC, which requires that a proportionate and effective response to plant health threats is established through a combination of technological, ecological and institutional management.

While well configured and correctly operated standard high-end machinery (Garcerá *et al.*, 2018 and Berger *et al.*, 2019) is already able to save in the order of 25% of pesticides (Berger *et al.*, 2022), the OPTIMA project aims for even higher saving in line with the EU's Green Deal (EC, 2019) and specifically working towards the *Farm to Fork* objective of 50% hazardous pesticide reduction by 2030 (EC, 2020).

One approach is to detect pests at a very early stage and then apply selective treatments only in those zones where pests are actually present. As *Vine downy mildew* (*Plasmopara viticola*) and *Apple scab* (*Venturia inaequalis*) are frequent endemic diseases that cause severe losses in specialty crops like grapes, and apples when not detected and treated at an early stage, these are at the core of OPTIMA trials and have, also been selected to develop an *early detection system* (EDS) prototype that in combination with a *decision support system* (DSS) produces *variable rate application* (VAR) maps. In the sequel, these VAR-maps can be downloaded to cloud connected spraying machinery such as FEDE's, so called, *Smartomizers* (Berger *et al.*, 2019) to perform zone-selective treatment. While, knowing that the majority of treatments against *Vine downy mildew* and *Apple scab* are of preventive and not of curative nature, working with these frequent pests at the core of the OPTIMA project allowed the OPTIMA partners to demonstrate that the underlying technologies and algorithms are able to support "Zone-Selective Plant Protection based on AI Pest Early Detection".

Materials and Methods

System Overview

Early pathogen infection detection is a vital part of IPM, and the OPTIMA *deep neural networks* based EDS, that contains Smart Camera GPS positioning and edge processing (see Figure 1), has been trained on RGB images as in Figure 2. Therewith, for every GPS geolocation the probability of disease presence, as displayed in Figure 3, can be estimated.

Disease probabilities at the different geolocations are conveyed over a cellular link from the EDS to the cloud based *decision support system* (DSS, <http://dss.optima-h2020.eu/>) as in Figure 1.

In general, the spread of disease severity varies significantly and without computer assistance, it is difficult to determine the optimal spraying space-time-window (Rossi *et al.*, 2012). Thus, in the past many DSS have been developed that take *local weather station* (LWS) data into account (Donatelli

et al., 2017). However, OPTIMA’s DSS goes beyond this state-of-the-art as it increases the prediction accuracy by additionally adopting data from the EDS.

Precisely, using spatial statistics interpolation methods, the EDS data is analysed to create the spatial-temporal distribution of an infection inside a field. The interpolation is made using four risk levels (from “no risk” to “maximum risk”), for projecting with a high accuracy the severity of the infection. Interpolation results are prescription maps in GeoJSON format that are sent through a dedicated *application programming interface* (API) to FEDE’s *Specialty Crops Platform* (SCP, <https://fedespecialtycropsplatform.com/>).

Figure 1. Conceptual system overview.

From the SCP, application maps are downloaded to the fleet of cloud connected sprayers, so called *Smartomizers* (Berger et al. 2019) with H_3O technology (Garcera et al. 2018). These *Smartomizers H₃O* then execute zone-selective plant protection.

From Figure 1 it also becomes apparent that FEDE sprayers with their proprietary *sprayer control system* (SCS) connect via *Wi-Fi* to an *Android based terminal* in the tractor’s cab (TAPP). The tractor carries also a *specialty crop gateway* (SCG) that guides the sprayer operator and connects tractor and sprayer via cellular modem to the Internet.

Moreover, farmers and advisors have access to the *Specialty Crops Platform* via a *web graphical user interfaces* (GUIs). This way, they can perform actions like sending prescriptions, or work orders to the sprayer operator, or monitoring results. Apart, through this GUI, back office staff can post-process data. For example, recording of all plant protection product treatments allows full treatment tractability and automatic farm book generation. Moreover, interoperability with other vendors and service providers is assured through a plurality of APIs, which allow data exchange,

for example, with third party *farm management information systems* (FMIS) and *enterprise resource planning* (ERP) tools.

Image Acquisition and Neural Network Training

From 2018 until 2020, hundreds of images of apple trees with and without scab were acquired in field station orchards from *Wageningen University & Research* as well as from an organic apple orchard both in the area of Randwijk, The Netherlands. At the field station, trees were inoculated while at the organic farm infections occurred naturally. Images were taken with the IDS U3-3800SE industrial machine vision camera using a Tamron 16 mm f/1.8 lens. Additionally, cell-phone images of apple scab infected apple leaves were obtained by OPTIMA partners in Spain in two different fields in the area of Èpila. The images were annotated using the open-source program *LabelImg* (<https://github.com/tzutalin/labelImg>) by the crop experts from the *Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya* (UPC) and *Wageningen Research* (WR). To increase the variation in the dataset and to potentially improve the generalization of the algorithm, 20 apple scab images of the open source *PlantVillage* dataset (Hughes D and Salathe M, 2016) were added to train the EDS.

Initial trials to detect *downy mildew* in grapes took also place in Turin (Italy) and the Piedmont area (Italy) in 2019. An IDS U3-3800SE 20 Mp RGB colour camera was transported to Turin and used to measure with *downy mildew* inoculated young grape plants grown in greenhouse compartments on the Turin University campus (*Universita Degli Studi Ditorino* (UNITO)). In total 146 RGB images of infected potted plants were obtained and a control group of 5 healthy plants was also imaged. Afterwards, the setup was transferred to a vineyard near Frassinello Monferrato (Italy) where images were taken at a distance of roughly 0.9 m from the leaves with natural infection. Areas of *downy mildew* were identified by the vineyard manager. Besides, in 2020, additional RGB images were taken by UNITO crop experts using normal cell phones, while the measurement setup with the high-resolution colour camera was sent to the *Agricultural University of Athens* (AUA) in Greece where artificial infected vines were imaged, resulting in 79 RGB images. In all images, the *downy mildew* spots were labelled with an encapsulating rectangular bounding-box by plant pathologists at AUA and UNITO using *LabelImg* (Figure 2).

Figure 2. *Example of an RGB image taken in grape vine. The two red bounding-boxes encapsulate the downy mildew spots on the leaf. The bounding-boxes were annotated by crop experts and used for algorithm training and evaluation.*

Results

EDS Prediction Accuracy

The EDS, as introduced in Figure 1, uses the open-source deep learning network called *You Only Look Once version 5* (YOLOv5, <https://github.com/ultralytics/yolov5>) (Redmon *et al.*, 2016). Therewith, the EDS is, *e.g.*, capable of identifying *downy mildew* probability as indicated on the EDS screen shot in Figure 3.

Figure 3. *EDS screen shot showing the camera image with disease detections probability (in this case 53% of downy mildew) at a specific GPS geolocation.*

It can be seen that one downy mildew spot was detected with a probability of 0.53 at a GPS position with Latitude 45.064965, and Longitude 7.591326. Similarly, all other geolocations get assigned a pest probability.

To evaluate the performance of the algorithm, the *Intersection over Union* (IoU) metric was used. It measures the overlap between the ground truth box and the predicted box and varies between zero in the case of no overlap and one in the case of full overlap. A threshold of 0.25 was chosen. This means, a detection hit with marginal overlap is sufficient to count as positive. The motivation is that the resolution of any industrial state of the art sprayer is much lower than the resolution of the image analysis and treatment efficacy is paramount.

The total number of *true positives* (TP), *false positives* (FP) and *false negatives* (FN) were determined. A TP is a diseased spot that is detected as such. An FP is background that is detected as diseased spot. An FN is a diseased spot that is not detected. As performance metric, *Precision*, *i.e.* the percentage of correct detections, is defined as $(TP / (TP+FP))$. Similarly, the *Recall* is defined as $(TP / (TP+FN))$ and is a metric for how well the algorithm can detect the totality of disease spots.

Algorithm performance results for *Apple scab* and *downy mildew* image-sets are presented in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Table 1. *Apple scab* confusion matrix. Precision is 81.8%. Recall is 90%.

Ground truth	YOLOv5 prediction		Total
	Apple scab	Healthy	
Apple scab	9 (TP)	1 (FN)	10
Healthy	2 (FP)	18 (TN)	20
Total	11	19	30

Table 2. *Downy mildew* confusion matrix. Precision is 91.8%. Recall is 95.7%.

Ground truth	YOLOv5 prediction		Total
	Downy mildew	Healthy	
Downy mildew	45 (TP)	2 (FN)	47
Healthy	4 (FP)	46 (TN)	50
Total	49	48	97

Épila Apple orchard EDS – Zone Spray (ZS) Proof of Concept

Turing to real world field trials, the selected pilot farm lies in *Épila*, Zaragoza (Spain). The region has been selected due to its relevance for apple production at national level. In addition, it is an area with high probability of suffering from natural *Apple scab* occurrence. A commercial plot supplying apples to the baby food industry was selected, which underlines the need for strictly ending up with zero residue.

Using the EDS on the pilot plot, it turned out that during the trial period (24/05/2021 to 31/07/2021) no *Apple scab* infestation was present, which was not only indicated by the EDS measurements, but was also confirmed by plant pathologists manually scouting the plot. Thus, the EDS correctly delivered a 0 % probability to the DSS as shown in Figure 4.

As the *Épila* fields are not experimental but 100% dedicated to commercial apple production, inoculation of *Apple scab* for trial purposes was not an option. To, nevertheless, perform a proof-of-concept, an artificial application map was generated in the DSS and was successfully transferred to the SCP as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4. *Apple scab* EDS detection probability in *Épila* trials.

Figure 5. Artificial application map as received in the Specialty Crops Platform (SCP).

From the SCP, the map information was downloaded to the SCS in the *OPTIMA Smart Sprayer* shown in Figure 6. It was then confirmed that the sprayer was able to switch electric valves and therewith spray liquid through the nozzles on in the marked zone of Figure 5, while no spray was applied in the surrounding area.

Figure 6. *OPTIMA Smart Sprayer* during *Épila* field trials.

Discussion

Although it is unfortunate that no *Apple scab* was present during the infield observation period, the work still demonstrates: a.) AI based disease detection is possible, with one of the biggest initial hurdles to obtain sufficiently large annotated data sets to train the neural networks.

b.) The OPTIMA consortium has been able to build the necessary IT, electronics, and mechanical infrastructure to carry out “Zone-Selective Plant Protection based on AI Pest Early Detection”.

c.) Early disease detection of *Apple Scab* and *Downy mildew* can be used to improve the decision support system accuracy. However, both pests are usually kept at bay with preventive treatments. Practical “Zone-Selective Plant Protection based on AI Pest Early Detection” must, thus, focus on different, locally contained pests for which effective curative plant protection products exist. In this case, the devised approach has significant potential to lower pesticide usage, and therewith to contribute to the Green Deal target of 50 % pesticide reduction by 2030.

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